

Research Article

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Does the internet add years to life? Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa

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Abstract: Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has the world's lowest life expectancy, which averages 62.7 years compared to 81.7 years in high-income countries. Internet use in SSA, though rising, remains significantly below global averages. Whether internet use has led to improvements in life expectancy in SSA is still uncertain. This study examined how internet use affected life expectancy across 41 SSA countries from 2000 to 2023. The Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) estimator was employed to address autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and cross-sectional dependence. Results indicate that a one percentage point increase in internet use is associated with about 0.09 additional years of life expectancy. However, these findings are conditional on other factors. Internet use yields greater health returns when institutional

quality is stronger, but exhibits diminishing returns as electricity access improves. Immunization, electricity access, and political stability positively affect life expectancy, while under-five mortality and health expenditure reduce it. This study recommends that governments pair digital connectivity initiatives with governance reforms, electrification, and health system strengthening to maximize population health gains across SSA.

Keywords – Digital health, Internet use, Life expectancy, Panel Corrected Standard Errors, Sub-Saharan Africa

1. INTRODUCTION

Life expectancy is a metric commonly employed to determine the well-being, socioeconomic environment, and development status of a country (Bayar et al., 2024). It is used as one of the inputs in computing the UN's Human Development Index (HDI) (Jahan et al., 2018). Increases in life expectancy indicate rising health standards, living conditions, and nutrition, while a decrease in life expectancy demonstrates societally relevant problems within a country's economic conditions. Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries have had the world's lowest life expectancy at birth for many years. Infant mortality has been high, and deaths from infectious disease, violence, and malnutrition have contributed to low life expectancy at birth. Life expectancy has been improving over recent decades in SSA, with falling HIV/AIDS prevalence and childhood disease prevalence. SSA countries have an average life expectancy of 62.7 years compared to high-income countries' average of 81.7 years (World Bank, 2024). SSA should continue efforts to increase life expectancy because of the positive effect it has on productivity and humanitarian reasons.

Increasing life expectancy has been shown to lead to more household and community investment in education and an increase in long-term economic activity (Folland et al., 2016).

In this regard, internet technology has started playing a significantly important role in determining population health indices such as life expectancy (Megbowon & David, 2023). Internet use may currently be lower in SSA than in other regions, but it is rising constantly and contributing to population health by being a vehicle for health information distribution, medical resource access, and digital health service provision (Byaro et al., 2023). The present study looks at the role of internet use as a potential driver of life expectancy in the 21st century. This study, therefore, asks the following research question: Can higher internet use help Sub-Saharan Africans live longer, healthier lives?

Research supports the association between internet use and living longer and having lower infant and under-five child mortality rates (Ahad et al., 2019; Majeed & Khan, 2019; Pu et al., 2025; Putteeraj et al., 2022). Increased internet access and mobile phone usage are associated with more robust health care systems and positive health education/public awareness and accessibility to remote health care services (Jarallah et al., 2024; Kaya et al., 2025). Internet use has its drawbacks for users' health as well. Problems associated with high-risk or inappropriate internet use include physical inactivity, mental health disorders, sleep disorders, misinformation, and social isolation (Sadagheyani & Tatari, 2021; Suarez-Lledo & Alvarez-Galvez, 2021; Ziebland et al., 2021). Therefore, associations between internet use and health-related outcomes are difficult to measure and have been met with unclear and conflicting results (Larnyo et al., 2020). Further research must be done to evaluate this relationship with objective and situation-dependent qualifiers to determine its effect in SSA, as epidemiologic trends, infrastructure, and institutional capacity differ among countries.

Even though studies in this regard have been carried out, significant gaps can still be found in the literature. For example, most extant studies focus on regions other than SSA, which differ significantly from others in terms of poor digital access, lower per capita income, and weaker health systems. Furthermore, on the methodological front, many of these studies do not account for potential endogeneity between internet use and health, while too few have accounted for cross-sectional dependence in panel studies (Kaya et al., 2025). Others have offered qualitative perspectives as opposed to econometric analyses. The current study contributes to filling these gaps by investigating the effect of internet use on life expectancy in SSA countries, empirically accounting for endogeneity and cross-sectional dependence via panel econometric techniques.

Findings from this study will have theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, this study will provide additional evidence on the roles that access to digital technology, as a determinant of health, plays in low-income contexts. On a more practical note, this study will provide data that can be utilized by policy-makers and other stakeholders seeking to achieve health gains via digital infrastructure and internet-based interventions.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1. Theoretical survey

Understanding how internet use affects life expectancy in Sub-Saharan Africa requires a theoretical analysis that captures the pathways through which digital connectivity influences health behavior, healthcare delivery, and the broader social determinants of health. Four complementary theories inform this study: the Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) framework, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DoIT), the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), and the Grossman Health Capital Model (GHCM). The Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) theory posits that social factors, including economic and physical environments, affect individual health and the health of populations, including their life expectancy (Marmot, 2020). Through this lens, internet use in SSA can be theorized as a social determinant because internet connectivity improves access to health information, minimizes travel distance to healthcare facilities, and allows populations to participate productively with healthcare systems. When communities lack access to connectivity services, health inequities widen socioeconomic gaps (Nutbeam & Lloyd, 2021).

Diffusion of Innovation Theory essentially maps out how technologies and ideas spread throughout populations over time, beginning with the earlier adopters of a particular innovation (Rogers, 2003). Used within the health

context in SSA, diffusion of innovation theory could allow us to understand how internet-mediated innovations spread throughout populations and are utilized to improve public health infrastructure. Some examples of internet-mediated health innovations could include telehealth software platforms, mobile health applications, and disease surveillance technologies. The speed and extent to which these innovations reach populations are dependent on many factors, including perceived usefulness, compatibility, and institutional support (Greenhalgh et al., 2017).

Bandura's social cognitive theory is centered around learning through observation, self-efficacy beliefs, and reinforcement of behaviors (Bandura, 1986). Health-promoting behaviors can be learned through online modeling channels that offer access to health education resources, social support systems, and behavior change techniques that can empower users to better their own health literacy and improve self-efficacy (Joseph et al., 2017). In SSA, this approach could prove useful in low-income communities with limited access to traditional health literacy resources (Nutbeam & Lloyd, 2021).

The Grossman Health Capital Model treats health as a form of durable capital stock that individuals invest in to extend their productive years and enhance their utility (Grossman, 1972). Under this model, internet use contributes to health investment by enabling individuals to access health information, communicate with healthcare providers, and use health-monitoring technologies. The model has been applied empirically to examine the relationship between health inputs and life expectancy in SSA (Fayissa & Gutema, 2005; Novignon & Akanni, 2016). It is the most appropriate theoretical anchor for this study for two reasons. First, it provides a rigorous economic framework that supports the quantitative analysis of the relationship between health inputs and outcomes. Second, it accommodates multiple determinants of health simultaneously, offering a comprehensive view of how internet use, alongside other inputs, shapes life expectancy in the region.

2.2. Empirical survey

Emerging evidence indicates that digital technologies can influence population health status. Evidence based on cross-country analyses has shown that ICT development has had a positive impact on health. For example, Majeed and Khan (2019), using panel data for 184 countries between 1990 and 2014, showed that ICT development (proxied by internet users, mobile phone subscriptions, and fixed telephone lines per 100 people) increased life expectancy at birth and decreased the infant mortality rate. Văidean and Achim (2022), using panel data for 185 countries between 2005 and 2018, also confirmed the positive effect of ICT development on life expectancy at birth and infant mortality rate. However, they found that the relationship between digital expansion and health status takes the shape of an inverted U.

Other research projects look more directly at how internet use may impact life expectancy. Pu et al. (2025) conducted a geographically and temporally weighted regression analysis of cross-country data from 182 countries between 1990 and 2020. They found that internet use significantly increased life expectancy across countries, but with heterogeneous effects. Kaya et al. (2025) employed fixed-effects and Pooled Mean Group Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PMG-ARDL) models on data from G7 countries. They found that both internet use and mobile subscriptions positively contributed to life expectancy through increasing individuals' access to healthcare information and improving digital health services. Both papers observed heterogeneity between regions.

Similar studies were done using datasets in developing countries. Byaro et al. (2023) employed the panel quantile regression method using a dataset from 48 developing countries in sub-Saharan Africa from 2000 to 2020. Their findings revealed that internet use increases life expectancy and decreases infant mortality and the under-five mortality rate in most quantiles. Their study concluded that individuals who access the internet were able to acquire improved health information and use health services. Köroğlu and Bayar (2026) found that improvement in Information Communications Technology (ICT), along with increased health expenditure, increases life expectancy in sub-Saharan Africa. Megbowon and David (2023) found that the development of ICT reduced the health gap in Africa through efficient healthcare services and increased access to health information.

Other studies document additional evidence on the broader development impact of digital technologies. For instance, Kouladoum (2024) used the system GMM estimation technique on panel data from 48 African countries spanning between 1980 and 2019. The authors discovered that internet use is significantly associated with human capital development. Dutta et al. (2019) show that ICT development has a positive impact on infant mortality among Asian countries. Overall, the evidence is consistent with the hypothesis that digital connectivity leads to improved health outcomes through knowledge diffusion, more communication, and access to health services.

Finally, some studies examine digital health interventions on a micro-level. Kabongo et al. (2021) showed support for mHealth interventions leading to higher utilization of maternal and child healthcare services by increasing health awareness and provider-patient communication. Larnyo et al. (2020) discovered improved health awareness and longevity when utilizing digital communication platforms (social media use included). Choi et al. (2012) provided support that internet-based interventions on an individual level decreased loneliness and depression in older adults, suggesting digital technologies can improve the mental well-being of older adults and increase social participation. Putteraj et al. (2022) discovered that healthcare professionals' readiness to adopt and use e-health technologies is influenced by innovation attributes like perceived compatibility and usefulness.

2.3. Literature summary and gaps

Existing evidence on the relationship between digital technologies and health outcomes suffers from at least four shortcomings. First, cross-country studies hide great regional diversity across developing countries. Second, research in this strand typically ignores cross-sectional dependence, thereby biasing the panel estimates. Third, past research did not sufficiently address the endogeneity between digital technology and health outcomes. Fourth, some studies use qualitative comparative approaches without conducting an econometric estimation. We close these gaps by providing evidence on how internet use improves population health and life expectancy in Sub-Saharan Africa based on econometric methods that address these issues.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) records the lowest life expectancy globally at 62.7 years old, lagging behind high-income countries by nearly 20 years. Internet use in SSA is increasing and is thought to facilitate access to health information and services, but there are limited comprehensive studies exploring how internet use affects life expectancy in the region. Existing studies largely focus on other geographic contexts that are not faced with SSA's digital, income, and healthcare access constraints. Furthermore, past analyses fail to account for the endogeneity between internet use and health outcomes while overlooking cross-sectional dependence in panel data setups, likely leading to biased estimates. In this study, we aim to bridge this gap by analyzing how internet use affects life expectancy in SSA. We use panel data from 41 SSA countries between 2000 and 2023 and employ panel econometric methods that account for these data issues.

Tables

Table 1: Variable name, description, and data sources

Variable	Description	Source
Life expectancy (LFE)	The average number of years a newborn is expected to live, use to measure of population health	WDI
Internet use (INT)	Percentage of the population accessing and utilizing the internet, reflecting the digital connectivity.	WDI
Health expenditure	Total health spending per capita (public and private) as a percentage of GDP, measuring resources allocated to healthcare.	WDI
Immunization	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	WDI
Under-5 mortality	Mortality rate, under-5 (per 1,000 live births)	WDI
Safe water	People using at least basic drinking water services (% of population)	WDI
Sanitation	People using at least basic sanitation services (% of population)	WDI
Electricity access	Access to electricity (% of population)	WDI

Government effectiveness	Government Effectiveness: Estimate	WDI
Political stability	Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism: Estimate	WDI

Source: Author's computation

Table 2: Slope homogeneity and cross-sectional dependence test results

Test procedure		Statistic value	Probability value
Pesaran and Yamagata (2008)	$\tilde{\Delta}$	-7.037	0.000
	$\tilde{\Delta}_{adj}$	-11.250	0.000
Blomquist and Westerlund (2013)	Δ_{HAC}	-9.445	0.000
	$(\Delta_{HAC})_{adj}$	-15.099	0.000
Pesaran's test		14.316	0.0000
Friedman		88.529	0.0000

Source: Author's computations

Table 3: Regression estimates: POLS

	POLS
Variables	Life expectancy
Life expectancy lagged one year	0.814*** (33.04)
Internet use	0.0260*** (2.90)
Internet use × Electricity access	-0.000436* (-1.80)
Internet use × Government effectiveness	0.00840 (0.98)
Health expenditure	-0.537** (-2.47)
Immunization	0.0174** (2.57)
Under-5 mortality	-0.642* (-1.70)
Sanitation	0.00285 (0.43)
Safe drinking water	-0.0173* (-1.86)
Electricity access	0.0101 (1.42)
Government effectiveness	-0.208 (-1.03)
Political stability	0.209 (1.47)
Constant	14.11*** (4.46)
Number of groups	41
Observations	943
R-squared	0.7454
Prob. F-Statistic	0.0000
Prob. Durbin statistic	0.4413
Prop. Wu-Hausman	0.4482
Minimum eigenvalue statistic	57.447
Prob. Sargan statistic	0.6448
Prop. Basman statistic	0.6491
Prob. Breusch-Pagan LM test	0.0000
Prob. Wooldridge test	0.0288
Prob. Modified Wald test	0.0000
Prob. Likelihood-ratio test	0.0000

t-statistics in parentheses; *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computations

Table 4: Regression estimates: PCSE, and FGLS

	(1)	(2)
	PCSE	FGLS
Variables	Life expectancy	Life expectancy
Life expectancy lagged one year	0.218 (1.363)	0.925*** (83.052)
Internet use	0.088*** (3.429)	0.004 (1.322)
Internet use × Electricity access	-0.002*** (-3.114)	-0.000 (-0.562)
Internet use × Government effectiveness	0.036** (2.468)	0.005** (2.509)
Health expenditure	-2.036*** (-3.860)	-0.049 (-0.800)
Immunization	0.046*** (2.590)	0.002 (1.211)
Under-5 mortality	-3.623*** (-3.280)	-0.438*** (-3.575)
Sanitation	-0.001 (-0.109)	-0.005** (-2.573)
Safe drinking water	-0.034 (-1.633)	-0.008*** (-2.777)
Electricity access	0.040*** (2.754)	0.001 (0.607)
Government effectiveness	-0.567* (-1.670)	-0.002 (-0.029)
Political stability	0.613** (2.512)	0.022 (0.660)
Constant	61.735*** (4.387)	6.935*** (5.901)
Number of groups	41	41
Observations	943	943
R-squared	0.7393	
Prob > chi2	0.0000	0.0000

t-statistics in parentheses; *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author's computations

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OR METHODS

4.1. Research design

This study employs a quantitative research design to investigate the effect of internet use on life expectancy in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The analysis covers 41 countries in SSA over a 24-year period (2000-2023), using annual country-level data from reputable international sources (see Table 1).

4.2. Study area, data types, and sample selection

The study employed panel data. The study period was between 2000 and 2023, hence covering 24 years. The sample consisted of 41 sub-Saharan countries (Appendix 4.1). The selected number of countries and the duration of the study's investigation were contingent on data availability. As such, the panel is balanced, making estimates cleaner by avoiding bias coming from missingness related to the outcome or regressors (attrition). It also simplifies the interpretation of results and improves the efficiency and reliability of inference due to reduced complications occasioned by irregular time patterns and unequal information across units (Baltagi, 2021).

4.3. Variables and their justification

4.3.1 Dependent variable

Life expectancy at birth was used as the outcome variable. Life expectancy at birth "is defined as the number of years a newborn infant would live if prevailing patterns of mortality at the time of its birth were to stay the same throughout its life" (World Bank, 2023). This variable has been used previously as an indicator of population health status (Angelakis et al., 2021; Kaya et al., 2025; Khan et al., 2024; Nkemgha et al., 2021; Pu et al., 2025).

4.3.2 Independent variable of interest

Internet use was the independent variable of interest. It measures improvements in prevention knowledge, care-seeking, and system responsiveness. Based on previous studies, this analysis expected a positive coefficient for

internet use (Kaya et al., 2025; Pu et al., 2025).

4.3.3 Control variables

Health expenditure and immunization were used in this study as measures of health system inputs. They were also expected to yield positive coefficients (Deshpande et al., 2014; Nkemgha et al., 2021; Radmehr & Adebayo, 2022; Rahman & Alam, 2022; Shattock et al., 2024). Under-5 mortality was used as a measure of disease burden and was expected to display a negative coefficient (Liang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2017). The study also used safe water and sanitation as measures of living conditions. These variables were anticipated to yield positive coefficients (Angelakis et al., 2021; Ummalla et al., 2022). Finally, electricity access, government effectiveness, and political stability were employed as measures of context and conversion environment. These variables were expected to show positive coefficients (Bunyaminu et al., 2022; Faisal et al., 2024; Khan et al., 2024).

4.4. Theoretical framework

This study adapts the Digital Capability Expansion Framework (DCEF) proposed by Sandberg (2014), Srivastava and Shainesh (2015), and Westerman et al. (2014) into a health-specific variant, termed the Digital Capability Expansion Theoretical Framework for Health (DCETF-H). The adaptation integrates two complementary theoretical traditions: Sen's (1999) capability approach, which defines capability as the freedom to fully participate in social and economic life, and Grossman's (1972) health production theory, which treats health as a form of capital stock in which individuals invest to maximize utility. Within the original DCEF, digital capability is defined as a collection of routines for strategizing by leveraging digital assets to create differential value. The DCETF-H extends this definition to the health domain by treating internet use as both a health-related capability and a productive input that enhances the efficiency of healthcare systems. Life expectancy serves as the primary health outcome, while the conversion of internet use into that outcome depends on effective enabling mechanisms.

The DCETF-H theorizes internet use in two related yet distinct ways. Firstly, internet use is a capability in its own right; the freedom to seek out, receive, and share information about health and to communicate digitally with healthcare systems. Internet use, therefore, influences people's opportunities to utilize real-time public health services within today's health environments. Conversely, denial of the internet can be understood as capability deprivation within the health domain (Benda et al., 2020; WHO, 2025). Second, internet use can be considered an instrumental resource able to enlarge the capability to reach and maintain one's health. As it reduces information and communication barriers, internet use enables disease prevention, early diagnosis, treatment adherence, responsiveness, etc. However, again following the capability approach, having access to this resource is not sufficient for achieving better health outcomes. The contribution of internet use to life expectancy depends on how this resource is used to pursue and achieve functionings beneficial to health (Robeyns, 2005; Sen, 1999).

A set of digital health endowments needs to exist for people to reap potential health benefits from internet use. These endowments include quality internet access; affordable digital devices and data plans; electricity; functioning online health services (e.g., telemedicine); and locally appropriate and accurate health information online. While these endowments allow digital health engagement to occur, they will not automatically lead to better outcomes (WHO, 2025).

These endowments are then acted on by a range of conversion factors at various levels to yield health capabilities that individuals can act upon. Personal-level factors include pre-existing health levels, age, digital health literacy, and personal preferences that affect their health choices. Societal factors include the income level of the household, gender norms, rural–urban disparities, availability of time, and perceived credibility of online information. Institutional factors include the quality of health governance, health service delivery, existing regulations that affect these areas, and data protection policies. Public goods that complement these, such as access to water and sanitation, reliable electricity, and transportation, also influence this layer of intervention.

Once converted, internet use affects life expectancy through four potential pathways. First is via health information and prevention channels; internet use increases health awareness about disease symptoms, risk factors, and preventive behaviors, enabling individuals to act swiftly and avoid unnecessary morbidity and mortality. Second is through the service and care-seeking channel, whereby internet use minimizes barriers to healthcare utilization through online consultation, appointment bookings, referrals, and follow-ups, hence averting diagnosis and treatment delays. Third are the health system efficiency and responsiveness mechanisms, where internet-enabled sources support disease surveillance, supply chain management, and rapid response to targeted diseases. Lastly, through behavioral and social support mechanisms whereby internet use enables treatment adherence, chronic disease management, and reproductive health practices (Benda et al., 2020). Combined, these mechanisms increase longevity by expanding the individuals' ability to survive (WHO, 2025).

DCETF-H points out that the internet can also lead to negative health effects. Exposure to harmful information through the internet, while having poor conversion factors, can lead to negative influences on our health. For example, misinformation leads people to hesitate to go for treatment or avoid vaccines altogether (Cinelli et al., 2020). Individuals will avoid using digital health services if they feel like their privacy is at risk or they don't trust the source. Health inequality can be impacted by digital health inequality. The more time we spend sedentary or looking at negative media, the lower the health of people over time (Brainard & Hunter, 2020).

Formally, let digital health endowments be denoted by D_H , health-specific conversion factors by C_H , effective health-related internet use by U_H , and life expectancy by LFE , with X_H representing non-digital health determinants. The framework can be summarized as:

$$U_H = f(D_H, C_H) \tag{1}$$

$$LFE = g(U_H, X_H) \tag{2}$$

4.5. Empirical model

Drawing on the above theoretical framework, the study employed Grossman's (1972) health production function. Grossman considered health as a capital stock which individuals acquire via investment in healthcare and non-healthcare inputs. People invest in medical and non-medical inputs to improve their health status, which improves their life expectancy and productivity, and maximizes their utility (Kaya et al., 2025). The Grossman (1972) model has been used in previous studies (Azam & Awan, 2022; Fayissa & Gutema, 2005; Kaya et al., 2025; Radmehr & Adebayo, 2022). Symbolically, the Grossman health production model is represented by Equation (3).

$$Y = f(X) \tag{3}$$

Where Y is the health outcome measured by life expectancy, while X is a vector of medical and non-medical inputs.

Equation (3) is a baseline equation. Fayisa and Gutema adopted and modified the Grossman (1972) model, making it able to incorporate more independent variables depending on the aim of the specific study. Therefore, this study employed the modified Grossman model to examine how internet use affects life expectancy in SSA in a dynamic sense while controlling for health expenditure, immunization, under-5 mortality, sanitation, safe drinking water, electricity access, government effectiveness, political stability, and the interaction of internet use and electricity access and government effectiveness. Internet use is hypothesized to have a positive effect on life expectancy. Equation (4) expresses the functional model of the study as follows:

$$LFE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LFE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 INT_{it} + \beta_3 (INT \times ELEC)_{it} + \beta_4 (INT \times GEFF)_{it} + \beta_5 HE_{it} + \beta_6 IMM_{it} + \beta_7 U5M_{it} + \beta_8 SAN_{it} + \beta_9 SDW_{it} + \beta_{10} ELEC_{it} + \beta_{11} GEFF_{it} + \beta_{12} POL_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{4}$$

Where LFE is life expectancy, INT is internet use, $INT \times ELEC$ is the interaction of internet use and electricity access, $INT \times GEFF$ is the interaction of internet use and government effectiveness, HE is health expenditure, IMM is immunization, $U5M$ is under-5 mortality, SAN is sanitation, SDW is safe drinking water, $ELEC$ is electricity access, $ELEC$ is government effectiveness, and POL is political stability.

The study applies log transformation to health expenditure and under-5 mortality to deal with the issue of data skewness, as shown in previous studies (Azam et al., 2022; Kaya et al., 2025). One-year lags are applied to structural inputs and health environment variables to reduce simultaneity and reflect delayed health effects. The model with logarithmically transformed health expenditure and under-5 mortality, together with lagged structural inputs, is represented by Equation (5).

$$LFE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LFE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 INT_{it} + \beta_3 (INT \times ELEC)_{it} + \beta_4 (INT \times GEFF)_{it} + \beta_5 HE_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 IMM_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 U5M_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 SAN_{i,t-1} + \beta_9 SDW_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} ELEC_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} GEFF_{i,t-1} + \beta_{12} POL_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

Where the variables are defined as before, β_0 is the constant, and ε_{it} represents the error term.

4.6. Estimation method

The paper employed the Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) estimation method proposed by Beck and Katz (Beck & Katz, 1995). The PCSE addresses autocorrelation, cross-sectional dependence, and heteroscedasticity, thus improving the efficiency of parameter estimates (Chen et al., 2010; Reed & Ye, 2011). The PCSE estimator retains the coefficient estimates from the linear panel model but adjusts the estimated variance-covariance matrix to account for cross-sectional dependence and panel-specific error structures. In this study, the estimation additionally imposes a first-order autoregressive correction, AR (1), within panels.

Accordingly, the empirical specification estimated is:

$$\hat{\beta}_{PCSE} = (X'X)^{-1}X'Y \quad (6)$$

with corrected variance-covariance matrix:

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{PCSE}) = (X'X)^{-1}X'\hat{\Omega}X(X'X)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\Omega}$ is the estimated panel-corrected covariance matrix of the disturbances.

The PCSE estimator is therefore preferred because it yields more reliable inference by correcting the variance-covariance matrix for these violations, while preserving the underlying coefficient estimates from the linear panel specification.

4.7. Estimation procedure

Descriptive statistics were performed to understand how the variables behaved over time (calculating, for example, measures of variation and dispersion). The study also verified the correlation among independent variables in order to reject those variables with a high correlation coefficient (equal to 0.8 and above, according to Green, 2018)). The study also computed the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), which measures the degree of multicollinearity in multiple variables. There exists multicollinearity if the average VIF exceeds 6 and an individual VIF exceeds 10 (Saadi, 2020).

The study conducted a slope homogeneity test using Blomquist and Westerlund (2013), and Pesaran and Yamagata (2008) delta tests. The $\tilde{\Delta}$ and $\tilde{\Delta}_{adj}$, and Δ_{HAC} and $(\Delta_{HAC})_{adj}$ tests reject the null hypothesis of slope homogeneity for p-values less than 0.05. As a result, the analysis would only proceed with second-generation panel data methods. This study also tested for cross-sectional dependence using Pesaran (2021) CD test. The test rejects the null hypothesis of no cross-sectional dependence if the p-value is less than 0.05. The CD test is represented by Equation (8).

$$CD = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}} (\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{\rho}_{ij}) \quad (8)$$

After the cross-sectional dependence test, the study also conducted the stationarity test. This was done to ensure the appropriate selection of the estimation strategy and valid statistical inference (Baltagi, 2021). The study used Pesaran (2007) CIPS is a second-generation unit root test that is effective in the presence of cross-sectional dependence. Equation (9) represents the CIPS statistic.

$$CIPS = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N t_i(N, T) \quad \text{and} \quad CIPS^* = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N t_i^*(N, T) \quad (9)$$

The estimation proceeded with the Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (POLS) as the baseline model. However, the POLS results present some shortcomings because it does not account for problems related to the error term. For example, there is heteroscedasticity, where the coefficient of the Breusch-Pagan test is significant. There is autocorrelation, indicated by the significant probability of the Wooldridge test. There is also a problem of cross-sectional dependence, as shown by the probabilities of the Pesaran and Friedman tests. With all the problems above, the study employed the Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) estimation method. PCSE has the ability to simultaneously address autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and cross-sectional dependence.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the analysis results, which include summary statistics depicting, among others, the mean, standard deviation, and range. There are also results of the pairwise correlations and variance inflation factors used to verify multicollinearity. Multicollinearity results are followed by regression estimation results and their interpretations, diagnostic tests, discussion, and, finally, a conclusion.

5.1. Descriptive statistics

Appendix 2 reports descriptive statistics for all variables. As can be seen from the results, life expectancy had a mean of 59.34 years with a moderately low standard deviation (SD = 7.03), demonstrating that there was significant variability in the health outcome variable across countries and years. Internet use had a low mean of 14.61% but with a high standard deviation (SD = 18.43), demonstrating that while most countries had low internet use rates, there were some countries with very high rates of internet use. The interaction variables, internet use × electricity access and internet use × government effectiveness, have high standard deviations and kurtosis. This can be explained by the large differences between countries in terms of digital infrastructure and institutional backgrounds. Regarding the control variables, the distribution of health expenditure is strongly positively skewed (3.624) and leptokurtic (kurtosis = 26.2). Immunization coverage has a mean of 74.84%. Likewise, under-five mortality has high variability and a positive skewness. Thus, some countries still face incredibly high levels of child mortality. Sanitation, safe water, electricity access, government effectiveness, and political stability all present high variability over observations. In general, we can see from the distributional properties that there are large differences across countries in terms of health, internet use, infrastructure, and institutions in our sample.

The study examined the multicollinearity problem using pairwise correlation. Appendix 3 indicates that all the pairwise correlation coefficient values were below 0.8, suggesting that multicollinearity was not a major issue. The mean VIF value also confirms that multicollinearity did not affect the entire model setup (see Appendix 4).

5.2. Slope homogeneity and cross-sectional dependence tests

Table 2 shows that the Pesaran and Yamagata (2008) and Blomquist and Westerlund (2013) tests rejected the null hypothesis of slope homogeneity. This justified the use of heterogeneous panel data estimators. Similarly, the Pesaran

and Friedman tests have rejected the null hypothesis of cross-sectional independence. This means that cross-sectional dependence poses a big obstacle, making the use of second-generation unit root tests appropriate.

5.3. Unit root test results

The study employed the Pesaran (2007) unit root test to check for stationarity after factoring in heterogeneity. The results of the unit root test in Appendix 5 reveal that the data were stationary at levels and first differences. Since there were no regressors integrated of order two, employing PCSE was justified.

5.4. Regression results and interpretation

The analysis began with the baseline results of the Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (POLS) estimator, presented in Table 3. However, the POLS estimates are subject to several limitations, as they do not account for key error term problems. Specifically, the Wooldridge and Breusch-Pagan tests returned significant probabilities, indicating the presence of autocorrelation. Heteroscedasticity was similarly detected through the Modified Wald and Likelihood-ratio tests. Furthermore, the Pesaran and Friedman tests revealed the presence of cross-sectional dependence. On a positive note, the model does not suffer from endogeneity, as confirmed by the Durbin and Wu-Hausman tests. The instruments employed are both valid, as evidenced by the Sargan and Basman tests, and strong, as indicated by the minimum eigenvalue statistic.

Given the diagnostics above, namely autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and cross-sectional dependence, the study applied the Panel Corrected Standard Error (PCSE) estimator. The PCSE results demonstrate overall efficiency, as confirmed by the significant Wald chi-square probability, which justifies the global significance of the estimated model. The coefficient of determination further indicates that approximately 74% of the variation in life expectancy across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) is jointly explained by the included explanatory variables. Accordingly, the PCSE results are treated as the main findings of the study, given their ability to address the sources of bias identified in the POLS estimates.

Table 4 presents the results of the PCSE regressions. Internet use is positively associated with life expectancy and statistically significant, with a coefficient of approximately 0.088 ($p < 0.01$). This means that internet use increasing by one percentage point is associated with an increase in life expectancy in SSA of about 0.09 years on average. Therefore, increased digital connectivity has a meaningful positive association with population health. Life expectancy is one measure of health and is necessary for increases in human capital. The positive relationship illustrated here indicates that internet use has value for well-being.

Moving to the interaction terms. The interaction term of internet use and electricity access is negative and significant (-0.002 , $p < 0.01$), suggesting that as electricity access improves, the marginal returns of internet use on life expectancy slightly decrease. Such a decline can be due to reasons such as diminishing marginal effects of internet use itself. On the other hand, internet use's interaction with government effectiveness is positive and significant (0.036 , $p < 0.05$), implying that better institutions strengthen the positive effect of internet use on health.

Moving on to control variables, health expenditure has a negative and significant coefficient (-2.036 , $p < 0.01$). It indicates that higher health expenditure lowers life expectancy in our sample. It could be that an increase in health expenditure by 1% will decrease life expectancy by 2.04 years. This could be because of the inefficient spending of funds used in improving health. It might also mean that countries with worse health conditions might increase their healthcare expenditure in an effort to combat prevalent diseases and illnesses. Under-five mortality also has a negative and significant coefficient (-3.623 , $p < 0.01$). It suggests that higher mortality among children lowers life expectancy significantly. It showcases the effect of child health on longevity.

Electricity access has a positive coefficient that is statistically significant (0.040 , $p < 0.01$). This indicates that increases in access to electricity increase life expectancy. This likely occurs due to increased provision of healthcare, healthier living conditions, and information about health. Government effectiveness's coefficient is negative and weakly significant (-0.567 , $p < 0.10$). This may indicate that differences in institutional quality play a role in explaining

differences in life expectancy. The negative sign may be capturing the complex nature of institutional environments or interaction with other development factors in sub-Saharan Africa. Political stability has a positive coefficient that is statistically significant (0.613, $p < 0.05$). This means that increases in political stability are associated with increases in life expectancy. Likely, this occurs because politicians can focus on the provision of services and longer-term policy when they are not concerned with suppressing political unrest.

Lastly, sanitation and access to improved water sources both have negative but insignificant coefficients (-0.001 and -0.034, respectively). These findings imply that holding all else constant, sanitation and access to safe drinking water do not have a statistically significant impact on life expectancy during the sample period. This is not to say that sanitation and safe drinking water are not important public health investments, just that they may operate through other institutional and structural factors.

5.5. Robustness checks

To test the sensitivity of the main results, we applied the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) estimator that controls for autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and cross-sectional dependence at the same time. It should be noted that the FGLS estimator can be used only when the time dimension is larger than the number of cross-sections in the panel data, and this is the reason why the PCSE results are primarily reported. The results based on the FGLS estimator support our main findings: internet use has a positive impact on life expectancy, and the signs of all coefficients do not change, which confirms the robustness of PCSE estimates.

5.6. Discussions

The estimated coefficient shows that internet use increases life expectancy in SSA. Its positive and significant coefficient also replicates the findings from cross-country regressions. For instance, Pu et al. (2025) estimated the impact of internet use on health outcomes and found that it improved health. Byaro et al. (2023) replicated these findings in Africa, such that increasing internet access saw life expectancy increase and mortality decrease. These findings are contrary to studies that have found negative impacts of internet use, such as Sadagheyani and Tatari (2021), Suarez-Lledo and Alvarez-Galvez (2021), and Ziebland et al. (2021). There are two likely reasons for the positive outcomes found in this study. One reason could be that using the internet allows people to gain greater access to health information. This information enables taking preventive action and seeking care in time. Likewise, when people are online, they create friends with whom they share health-related matters. This results in social bonding, which reduces stress and supports mental health.

The interaction between internet use and electricity access has a significant negative effect on life expectancy. This result may reflect diminishing returns in environments where basic infrastructure is already relatively developed. While the literature on this specific interaction remains limited, some studies have suggested that digital technologies tend to generate larger marginal benefits in infrastructure-poor environments where access to information is initially limited (Hilbert, 2016). In such contexts, the introduction of internet services may significantly reduce information gaps and improve access to healthcare guidance (Aker & Mbiti, 2010). However, as infrastructure improves, the incremental health benefits of additional internet use may become smaller.

Conversely, internet use interacts positively and significantly with government effectiveness. This suggests that institutional quality amplifies the effect of internet use on life expectancy. This finding echoes literature on the primacy of effective governance and institutions' capability for society to benefit optimally from digital technologies (Frey & Osborne, 2017; West, 2005). It can be inferred that nations with solid institutions are able to better incorporate internet usage into healthcare systems that allow rapid circulation of health information and services.

Health expenditure has a negative and statistically significant effect on life expectancy. This result contrasts with the conventional expectation that higher health spending should improve health outcomes. Many previous studies have documented a positive relationship between health expenditure and life expectancy (Bloom & Canning, 2000; Radmehr & Adebayo, 2022; Suhrcke et al., 2006). Therefore, the negative relationship observed in this study may

reflect inefficiencies in health spending and weak health systems in SSA. There could also be a possibility that higher expenditure is driven by the need to respond to existing health crises rather than preventive healthcare improvements. This interpretation is consistent with findings from some developing-country studies, which suggest that increased health spending does not always translate into improved health outcomes when institutional capacity and health system efficiency are limited (Deshpande et al., 2014; Nkemgha et al., 2021).

The positive and significant effect of immunization on life expectancy corroborates the findings of Rahman and Alam (2022) and Shattock et al. (2024), affirming immunization as a vital determinant of population health. Likewise, the negative and significant effect of under-five mortality is consistent with both theoretical expectations and a broad body of empirical evidence demonstrating that reductions in child mortality substantially improve overall life expectancy (Liang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2017).

The positive and statistically significant coefficient of electricity access also conforms to previous research highlighting access to infrastructure as a determinant of health (Atun et al., 2015; Bunyaminu et al., 2022). Electricity access increases the reliability of healthcare service provision, as hospitals can use it to power necessary equipment and store vaccines. Electricity also allows households to connect to technologies that can increase their consumption of digital information about health.

Political stability has a positive and statistically significant effect on life expectancy. This result is in line with prior literature. One reason that could explain this result is good governance, the implementation of persistent health policies, and improvements in social services delivery due to political stability. As Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) state, political institutions have long-term effects on growth and welfare, which includes life expectancy. With political stability, governments can concentrate on investing in healthcare and improving the delivery of social services.

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The strong and positive association between internet use and life expectancy ($\beta = 0.088$, $p < 0.01$) offers concrete empirical support for treating digital health as part of a nation's overall health environment. Policies aiming to improve population health should incorporate internet-enabled technologies such as telehealth, mHealth, digital disease detection, and online health information provision into primary and community care settings, with special focus on rural or underserved areas where informational gaps, and therefore marginal health improvements, are the largest.

The positive and significant interaction between internet use and government effectiveness ($\beta = 0.036$, $p < 0.05$) indicates that institutional quality is a multiplier of the health benefits of internet use. Governance reforms that improve accountability, transparency, and efficiency in health system management, including stronger public financial management for health spending, anti-corruption measures in drug procurement, and improved data systems for health surveillance, are essential to realizing the full health returns from internet investment.

Deaths among children less than age 5 significantly decrease life expectancy ($\beta = -3.623$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that child survival is the strongest driver for increasing population-wide longevity. Continued investment in vaccination programs (robustly determined to have a positive significant effect at $\beta = 0.046$, $p < 0.01$), improved nutrition, and maternal health services is essential. Governments should protect immunization program financing from budget cuts during fiscal downturns and increase their use of digital channels to deliver life-saving vaccines to everyone, everywhere. Electricity access also has a robust positive relationship with life expectancy ($\beta = 0.040$, $p < 0.01$), further underscoring the urgency of electrifying health care facilities for vaccine cold-chain storage and medical technology.

Political stability has a positive and significant effect on life expectancy ($\beta = 0.613$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that conflict prevention and peace-sustaining governance are health investments. Governments should factor political stability into the design of health system strengthening programs, prioritizing resilient health infrastructure and community health worker networks that can continue to function during periods of political disruption.

7. CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

7.1. Contributions to the scientific community

Our study contributes to the literature on digitalization and population health in three main aspects. Methodologically, this paper overcomes the panel models' limitations of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and cross-sectional dependence by employing the PCSE estimator with AR(1) correction to produce unbiased causal estimates, whereas earlier panel studies could not. Theory-wise, this study anchors our analysis on the Digital Capability Expansion Theoretical Framework for Health (DCETF-H), which extends the DCETF into the health context by integrating Sen's capability approach with Grossman's health capital model. Lastly, on empirical grounds, we find that the benefits of digital connectivity on health only materialize in contexts where citizens have access to electricity and high-quality governance institutions. The relationship between internet use and life expectancy is, therefore, conditional on a country's political and economic development levels.

7.2. Contributions to future research

This paper leaves room for numerous opportunities for future research. Although the PCSE estimator was used to account for cross-sectional dependence and heteroscedasticity in the error term, future researchers may want to consider causal identification strategies such as instrumental variable techniques or difference-in-differences methodology to pinpoint the causal impact of internet use on life expectancy. Researchers can also disaggregate internet use into type and purpose (mobile internet vs. broadband internet and looking for health information vs. social media use, respectively) to identify what aspect of digital adoption may affect health outcomes the most. Future studies could further explore the conditional relationship between internet use and health outcomes by governance indicators and electricity access, which we identify as moderators of the positive relationship between internet use and life expectancy. Given our regional panel analysis, country case studies, and sub-national analyses, we may reveal interesting disparities in how internet use affects health outcomes. Lastly, the usage of micro-level household survey data in addition to our macro panel would allow future researchers to establish what behaviors and service accesses mediate the relationship between internet use and life expectancy in SSA.

8. CONCLUSION

Results from this study corroborate the growing body of literature that emphasizes internet usage as key to increasing life expectancy. However, some of the findings, like the negative effect of health expenditure and the insignificant effect of sanitation and safe water, reveal that health investments and access to improved infrastructure may need complementary institutional and structural features to be fruitful across SSA countries. As such, our results lend support to policies that pair digital expansion with enhanced governance, infrastructure, and health system efficiency.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Countries used in the study

Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo Republic, Democratic Republic of Congo, Cote d'Ivoire, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Seychelles, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zimbabwe

Appendix 2: Summary statistics (Observations=984) – Original variables

	Obs	Std.Dev.	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Life expectancy	984	7.025	59.341	59.69	14.665	77.237	-.447	5.48
Internet use	984	18.433	14.605	6.373	.006	87.401	1.683	5.331
Internet use × Electricity access	943	687.292	362.422	183.529	-484.285	4443.172	3.044	13.597
Internet use × Government effectiveness	943	15.309	4.753	.696	-20.502	116.581	3.376	17.596
Health expenditure	984	3.075	5.488	4.699	.891	34.405	3.624	26.2
Immunization	984	16.664	74.837	76	16	99	-.646	2.904
Under-5 mortality	984	45.73	85.196	78.1	11.6	478.9	1.386	9.87
Sanitation	984	22.563	34.092	29.072	2.966	99.7	1.05	3.681
Safe water	984	17.243	64.182	63.849	18.759	99.902	.01	2.391
Electricity access	984	27.265	39.718	35.3	1.3	100	.607	2.352
Government effectiveness	984	.612	-.709	-.763	-1.881	1.15	.604	3.009
Political stability	984	.848	-.467	-.347	-2.729	1.283	-.248	2.463

Source: Author's computations

Appendix 3: Matrix of correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1) Internet use	1.00										
(2) Internet use × Electricity access	0.75***	1.00									
(3) Internet use × Government effectiveness	0.58***	0.78***	1.00								
(4) Health expenditure	0.03	-0.01	0.01	1.00							
(5) Immunization	0.33***	0.21***	0.21***	0.20***	1.00						
(6) Under-5 mortality	-0.58***	-0.28***	-0.23***	-0.03	-0.57***	1.00					
(7) Sanitation	0.62***	0.49***	0.49***	0.13***	0.54***	-0.60***	1.00				
(8) Safe drinking water	0.61***	0.36***	0.36***	0.10***	0.46***	-0.63***	0.72***	1.00			
(9) Electricity access	0.71***	0.44***	0.39***	-0.06*	0.36***	-0.69***	0.72***	0.82***	1.00		
(10) Government effectiveness	0.40***	0.39***	0.37***	0.01	0.51***	-0.49***	0.60***	0.50***	0.53***	1.00	
(10) Political stability	0.32***	0.26***	0.20***	0.05*	0.49***	-0.46***	0.45***	0.56***	0.48***	0.67***	1.00

Source: Author's computations

Appendix 4: Variance inflation factors

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Electricity access	6.11	0.163728
Internet use	4.48	0.223166
Internet use × Electricity access	4.43	0.225684
Under-5 mortality	4.24	0.235641
Safe drinking water	4.2	0.236743
Sanitation	3.53	0.283474
Internet use × Government effectiveness	2.77	0.360930
Government effectiveness	2.51	0.398243
Political stability	2.34	0.428123
Immunization	2.10	0.475471
Health expenditure	1.29	0.773332
Mean VIF	3.46	

Source: Author's computations

Appendix 5: Unit root test results

Variables	Statistic	Critical value	Order of integration
Δ Life expectancy	-3.583	-2.11	I (1)

Δ Internet use	-3.119	-2.11	I (1)
Δ Internet use \times Electricity access	-3.996	-2.11	I (1)
Δ Internet use \times Government effectiveness	-3.713	-2.11	I (1)
Δ Health expenditure	-4.340	-2.11	I (1)
Immunization	-2.693	-2.11	I (0)
Under-5 mortality	-2.496	-2.11	I (0)
Δ Sanitation	-2.923	-2.11	I (1)
Δ Safe drinking water	-2.506	-2.11	I (1)
Electricity access	-2.823	-2.11	I (0)
Government effectiveness	-2.233	-2.11	I (0)
Political stability	-2.512	-2.11	I (0)

Source: Author's computations